

Neutrosophic Pre- α , Semi- α & Pre- β Irresolute Functions

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Abstract: Smarandache introduced and developed interesting concepts Neutrosophic set from the Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. A.A. Salama introduced NTSs and continuity. Aim of this paper is we introduce and study the concepts Neutrosophic Pre- α , Semi- α & Pre- β Irresolute Functions and its Properties are discussed details.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Irresolute Functions, Neutrosophic Pre- α , Neutrosophic Semi- α , Neutrosophic Pre- β Irresolute Functions.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophic concepts have wide range of applications in the area of decision making Artificial Intelligence, Information Systems, Computer Science, Medicine, Applied Mathematics, Mechanics, Electrical & Electronic and, Management Science, etc. In 1980s the international movement called paradoxism based on contradictions in science and literature, was founded by Smarandache[15,16], who then extended it to neutrosophy, based on contradictions and their neutrals. The mapping is the one of the important concept in topology. Neutrosophic sets have three kind like T Truth, F -Falsehood, I- Indeterminacy. Neutrosophic topological spaces (N-T-S) introduced by Salama [27,28]etal., by using Smarandache neutrosophy set. In this Paper new type of functions called as Neutrosophic Pre- α irresolute functions, Neutrosophic Pre- α , Semi- α and Pre- β Irresolute Functions. Also the interrelationships of these functions with the other existing functions are established. Several characterizations and some interesting properties of these classes of functions are given

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we provide basic definition and operation of Neutrosophic sets and its Results
Definition 2.1 [15,16] Let X_N be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic set \mathcal{E}_1^* is a object having the form

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \rangle : x \in X_N \},$$

$\mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x)$ - membership function

$\sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x)$ - indeterminacy and then

$\gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x)$ - non-membership function

Definition 2.2 [15,16].Neutrosophic set $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$, on $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$ and $\forall x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$$

1. $\mathcal{E}_1^* \cap \mathcal{E}_2^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \cap \mu_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \cap \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \cup \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$
2. $\mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \cup \mu_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \cup \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \cap \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$
3. $\mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^* \Leftrightarrow \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \leq \mu_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \leq \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x) \& \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \geq \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_2^*}(x)$
4. the complement of \mathcal{E}_1^* is $\mathcal{E}_1^{*C} = \{ \langle x, \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), 1 - \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$

Definition 2.3 [28].Let $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$ be non-empty set and $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}$ be the collection of Neutrosophic subsets of $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$ satisfying the following properties:

1. $0_{\mathcal{N}}, 1_{\mathcal{N}} \in \tau_{\mathcal{N}}$
3. $T_1 \cap T_2 \in \tau_{\mathcal{N}}$ for any $T_1, T_2 \in \tau_{\mathcal{N}}$
4. $\cup T_i \in \tau_{\mathcal{N}}$ for every $\{T_i : i \in j\} \subseteq \tau_{\mathcal{N}}$

Then the space $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \tau_{\mathcal{N}})$ is called a Neutrosophic topological spaces (N-T-S).

The element of $\tau_{\mathcal{N}}$ are called Ne.OS (Neutrosophic open set)

and its complement is Ne.CS(Neutrosophic closed set)

Example 2.4.Let $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} = \{x\}$ and $\forall x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$

$$A_1 = \langle x, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \rangle, A_2 = \langle x, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}, \frac{9}{10} \rangle$$

$$A_3 = \langle x, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10} \rangle, A_4 = \langle x, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{9}{10} \rangle$$

Then the collection $\tau_{\mathcal{N}} = \{0_{\mathcal{N}}, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, 1_{\mathcal{N}}\}$ is called a N-T-S on $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$.

Definition 2.5.Let $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \tau_{\mathcal{N}})$ be a N-T-S and $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$ be a

Neutrosophic set in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Then \mathcal{E}_1^* is named as

1. Neutrosophic b closed set [20] (Ne.bCS) if $\text{Ne.cl}(\text{Ne.int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \cap \text{Ne.int}(\text{Ne.cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^*$,
3. Neutrosophic α -closed set [7] (Ne. α CS) if $\text{Ne.cl}(\text{Ne.int}(\text{Ne.cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^*$,
4. Neutrosophic pre-closed set [30] (Ne.Pre-CS) if $\text{Ne.cl}(\text{Ne.int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^*$,
5. Neutrosophic regular closed set [7] (Ne.RCS) if $\text{Ne.cl}(\text{Ne.int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) = \mathcal{E}_1^*$,
5. Neutrosophic semi closed set [17] (Ne.SCS) if $\text{Ne.int}(\text{Ne.cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^*$,

Definition 2.6.[9] $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \tau_{\mathcal{N}})$ be a N-T-S and $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \sigma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x), \gamma_{\mathcal{E}_1^*}(x) \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \}$ be a

Neutrosophic set in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Then

Neutrosophic closure of \mathcal{E}_1^* is $\text{Ne.Cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \cap \{H : H \text{ is a Ne.CS in } \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \text{ and } \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq H\}$

Neutrosophic interior of \mathcal{E}_1^* is $\text{Ne.Int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \cup \{M : M \text{ is a Ne.OS in } \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \text{ and } M \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^*\}$.

Definition 2.7. Let $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{J}_{\mathcal{N}})$ be an NTS and A be an NS in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$.

The Neutrosophic β -closure & β -interior of A are defined by

- (i) $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \cap \{ \mathcal{E}_3^* : \mathcal{E}_3^* \text{ is a } \beta\text{CS in } \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \text{ and } \mathcal{E}_3^* \supseteq \mathcal{E}_1^* \}$;

(ii) $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \cup\{\mathcal{E}_4^* : \mathcal{E}_4^* \text{ is a } \mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS in } \mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}} \text{ and } \mathcal{E}_4^* \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^*\}.$

Lemma 2.8.

Let \mathcal{E}_1^* be an NS in NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$. Then

- (i) $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{NP int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \text{NPcl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$
- (ii) $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{Naint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \text{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$
- (iii) $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{NSint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \text{NScl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$
- (iv) $\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\beta\text{int}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$.

Proof: It is easy to prove.

3. Neutrosophic Pre- α , Semi- α & Pre- β Irresolute Functions

In this section Neutrosophic pre- α -irresolute, semi- α -irresolute, Neutrosophic pre- β -irresolute functions are defined. Also, the relationships of these functions with the other existing functions are studied.

Definition 3.1.

A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ from an NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ is named as Neutrosophic β -irresolute if $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ in $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ for each $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$.

Definition 3.2 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ from an NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ is named as Neutrosophic pre- α -irresolute if $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is an NPOS in $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ for each $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$.

Definition 3.3 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ from an NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ is named as Neutrosophic α -irresolute if $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ for each $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$.

Definition 3.4 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ from an NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ is named as Neutrosophic semi- α -irresolute if $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is an NSOS in $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ for each $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$.

Definition 3.5 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ from an NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ is named as Neutrosophic pre- β -irresolute if $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NPOS in $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ for each $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$.

Proposition 3.6 Every $\text{N}\alpha$ -irresolute function is Npre- α (NSemi- α , resp.)-irresolute function.

Proof: Let $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ be $\text{N}\alpha$ -irresolute function from NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$. Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in $\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Since \check{f} is $\text{N}\alpha$ -irresolute function, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Every $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ is NPOS (NSOS, resp.). So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NPOS (NSOS, resp.) in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Hence \check{f} is Npre- α (NSemi- α , resp.)-irresolute function.

Proposition 3.7 Every Npre- β -irresolute function is Npre- α -(Npre, resp.) irresolute function.

Proof: Let $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ be Npre- β irresolute function from NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$. Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ (NPOS resp.) in $\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Every $\text{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ (NPOS, resp.) is $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$. Since \check{f} is Npre- β -irresolute function, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NPOS in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Hence \check{f} is Npre- α -(Npre, resp.) irresolute function.

Proposition 3.8 Every Npre- β -irresolute function is $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -irresolute function.

Proof: Let $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$ be Npre- β irresolute function from NTS $(\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}})$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{N}})$. Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be βOS . Since \check{f} is Npre- β -irresolute function, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NPOS in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. As every NPOS is $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ in $\mathcal{X}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Hence \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -irresolute function.

Proposition 3.9 Every Nirresolute function is NS- α -irresolute function.

Proof: Let $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ be Nirresolute function from $\text{NTS}(\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N)$ to another $\text{NTS}(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Every NaOS is NSOS . Since \check{f} is Nirresolute function, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is $\text{NS-}\alpha$ -irresolute function.

Example 3.10 Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{Y}_N = \{c, d\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_1^*, 1\}$, $\Gamma_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_2^*, 1\}$, are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N respectively where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle.$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

Define an Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. By $\check{f}(a) = d, \check{f}(b) = c$ \mathcal{E}_2^* is a NOS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. So \mathcal{E}_2^* is NaOS , NPOS , and NBOS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

, since $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle x, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle$ is an NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = 1_N$$

Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))) = 1_N$

So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NBOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is $\text{Npre-}\beta$ -irresolute, Npre irresolute function, $\text{Npre-}\alpha$ -irresolute function and NB -irresolute function. Also \check{f} is a N precontinuous and NB -continuous. As $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))) = 0_N, \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \not\subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))))$

$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is not NaOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \not\subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = 0_N$. implies $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is not NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is not $\text{N}\alpha$ -irresolute function, not $\text{NSemi-}\alpha$ -irresolute function, not $\text{N}\alpha$ -continuous, not NSemi continuous, and not Nirresolute function.

Example 3.11

Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{Y}_N = \{c, d\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_1^*, 1\}$, $\Gamma_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_2^*, 1\}$, are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N respectively is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle.$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_3^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right) \rangle$$

is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

Define a Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ by $\check{f}(a) = d, \check{f}(b) = c$ \mathcal{E}_2^* is a NOS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. Also \mathcal{E}_2^* is NaOS , NPOS and NSOS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle x, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle$$

and $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \mathcal{E}_1^*$. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))))$ This implies $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NaOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NPOS and NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is a $\text{N}\alpha$ -irresolute

function, NS- α -irresolute function, Npre- α -irresolute function, N α -continuous, NSemicontinuous, and Nprecontinuous. $\mathcal{E}_3^* \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$. So \mathcal{E}_3^* is a NSOS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}) \rangle$. Then $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))) = \mathcal{E}_1^*$

. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is not N α OS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is not Nstrongly α -continuous.

Example 3.12 Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{Y}_N = \{c, d\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_1^*, 1\}$, $\Gamma_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_2^*, 1\}$, are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N respectively, where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, (\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}), (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle.$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle y, (\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle$$

Define a Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$. By $\check{f}(a) = d$, $\check{f}(b) = c$. \mathcal{E}_2^* is a NOS in \mathcal{G}_N . Hence \mathcal{E}_2^* is N α OS, NPOS, NSOS and N β OS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$.

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle x, (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle$$

$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}$ implies $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a N β OS in

\mathcal{X}_N , since $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}$. Hence \check{f} is Nirresolute function, NS- α -irresolute function, NSemi continuous and N β -continuous. $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \mathcal{E}_1^*$. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is not N α OS in \mathcal{X}_N . Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is not NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is not N α -irresolute function, not Npre- α -irresolute function, not Npre irresolute function, not Npre- β -irresolute function, not N α -continuous and not Npre continuous.

Example 3.13

Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b, c\} = \mathcal{Y}_N$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \mathcal{E}_1^*, \mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*, \mathcal{E}_1^* \cap \mathcal{E}_2^*\}$, $\Gamma_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \mathcal{E}_3^*\}$ are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}) \rangle.$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle x, (\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{7}{10}) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_3^* = \langle y, (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}), (\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_4^* = \langle y, (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}) \rangle$$

is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Define an identity Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$. \mathcal{E}_3^* is a NOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . and $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \langle x, (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}), (\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}) \rangle$

$\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = \mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is a N α OS in $(\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N)$. Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is NPOS, NSOS and N β OS in \mathcal{X}_N . Therefore \check{f} is N α -continuous, Npre continuous, NSemicontinuous and N β -continuous. \mathcal{E}_4^* is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $\mathcal{E}_4^* \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) = 1_N$. Hence \mathcal{E}_4^* is a N α OS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Also \mathcal{E}_4^* is NPOS, NSOS and N β OS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*) = \langle x, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle$$

And $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is NSOS and also $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$

in \mathcal{X}_N . So \check{f} is Nirresolute function, NS- α -irresolute function and $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -irresolute function. Since $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) = \mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*$, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is not $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ in \mathcal{X}_N and $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) = \mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*$, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is not NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is not $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute function, not Npre- α -irresolute function and not Npre- β -irresolute function.

Example 3.14

Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{Y}_N = \{c, d\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_1^*, 1\}$, $\Gamma_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_2^*, 1\}$, are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N respectively where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\text{And } \mathcal{E}_3^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{6}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right) \rangle$$

is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Define a Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$. By $\check{f}(a) = d$, $\check{f}(b) = c$, \mathcal{E}_2^* is

a NOS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$. And $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle y, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$ and

$\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is

an NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N , which implies \check{f} is NSemi continuous and also \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -continuous. \mathcal{E}_3^* is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Also $\mathcal{E}_3^* \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = 1_N$ which implies \mathcal{E}_3^* is a $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Hence \mathcal{E}_3^* is NPOS,

NSOS and $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \langle y, \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$ So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is a NPOS and $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ in

\mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is Npre- α -irresolute function, Npre- β -irresolute function and $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -irresolute function.

Since $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = \mathcal{E}_1^*$, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is not $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \not\subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}$. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is not NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is not $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute function, not Nirresolute function, and not NS- α -irresolute function.

Example 3.15

Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\} = \mathcal{Y}_N$ and

$$\mathcal{T}_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \mathcal{E}_1^*, \mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*, \mathcal{E}_1^* \cap \mathcal{E}_2^*\}$$

$\Gamma_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \mathcal{E}_3^*\}$ are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right) \rangle.$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle x, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_3^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_4^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle,$$

is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Define an identity Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. \mathcal{E}_3^* is a NOS in

$$\mathcal{Y}_N \dots \mathcal{E}_3^* \text{ is a NOS, N}\alpha\text{OS, NPOS in } (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N). \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \langle y, (\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}) \rangle$$

So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is a N α OS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is NPOS and NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is N α -irresolute, Nsemi- α -irresolute and Npre- α -irresolute function, N α -continuous, Nprecontinuous and NSemi continuous. \mathcal{E}_4^* is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}$. Hence $\mathcal{E}_4^* \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$. Thus \mathcal{E}_4^* is a NSOS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*) = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{3}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle$$

and $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) = \overline{\mathcal{E}_1^* \cup \mathcal{E}_2^*}$

. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*) \not\subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)))$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is not NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is not Nirresolute function.

Example 3.16

Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b, c\} = \mathcal{Y}_N$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \mathcal{E}_1^*\}, \Gamma_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \mathcal{E}_2^*\}$ are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}) \rangle.$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle x, (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}) \rangle.$$

Define a Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ by $\check{f}(a) = b, \check{f}(b) = c, \check{f}(c) = a$.

\mathcal{E}_2^* is a NOS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. Also \mathcal{E}_2^* is N α OS, NPOS, NSOS and N β OS in \mathcal{Y}_N and

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}), (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}) \rangle$$

$\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = 1_N$. Since $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$, is a NPOS in $(\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N)$ and also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is N β OS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is a Npre irresolute function, Npre- α -irresolute function, Npre continuous and N β -continuous. Now $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \not\subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = 0_N$. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is not NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Also $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))) = 0_N$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is not N α OS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is not N α -irresolute function, not NS- α -irresolute function and not N α -continuous and not NSemi continuous.

Example 3.17 Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\}$ $\mathcal{Y}_N = \{c, d\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_1^*, 1\}, \Gamma_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_2^*, 1\}$, are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N respectively where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}), (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle y, (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}), (\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_3^* = \langle y, (\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}), (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle$$

is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Define an Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. by $\check{f}(a) = c, \check{f}(b) = d$. \mathcal{E}_2^* is a NOS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$. Also \mathcal{E}_2^* is N α OS, NPOS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle x, (\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}) \rangle$$

and $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = 1_N$.

Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N .

Now $\mathcal{E}_3^* \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)) = 1_N$ Therefore \mathcal{E}_3^* is an NPOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Also \mathcal{E}_3^* is an N β OS in \mathcal{Y}_N

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \langle x, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}\right), \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = 0_N$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))$.

Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is not an NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . So \check{f} is not Npre- β -irresolute function and \check{f} is not Npre-irresolute function. Since $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \not\subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = 0_N$.

$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is not N β OS in \mathcal{X}_N . So \check{f} is not N β -irresolute function.

Example 3.18 Let $\mathcal{X}_N = \{a, b\}$, $\mathcal{Y}_N = \{c, d\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_1^*, 1\}$, $\Gamma_N = \{0, \mathcal{E}_2^*, 1\}$, are NTS on \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{Y}_N respectively where

$$\mathcal{E}_1^* = \langle x, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{2}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_2^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

$$\mathcal{E}_3^* = \langle y, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Define an Neutrosophic function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$ by $\check{f}(a) = c$, $\check{f}(b) = d$. \mathcal{E}_2^* is a NOS in $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \Gamma_N)$. Also \mathcal{E}_2^* is N α OS, NPOS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \langle x, \left(\frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right), \left(\frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

and $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = 1_N$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Therefore \check{f} is a Npre-irresolute, Npre- α -irresolute and Npre-continuous.

\mathcal{E}_3^* is a NS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $\mathcal{E}_3^* \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = \bar{\mathcal{E}}_2^*$. Hence \mathcal{E}_3^* is a N β OS in \mathcal{Y}_N .

$$\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) = \langle x, \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{4}{10}\right), \left(\frac{2}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{5}{10}\right) \rangle$$

and $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = 0_N$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \not\subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))$. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is not an NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is not Npre- β -irresolute function.

Diagram: I

4.PROPERTIES

Theorem 4.1 If a function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ is Npre- α -irresolute (N α -irresolute and NS- α -irresolute, resp.) then $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$ is \mathcal{NPCS} (N α -closed and NSemiclosed, resp.) in \mathcal{X}_N for any N nowhere dense set \mathcal{E}_1^* of \mathcal{Y}_N .

Proof:

Let \mathcal{E}_1^* be an N nowhere dense set in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) = 0_N$. Now, $\overline{\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))} = 1_N \Rightarrow \overline{\text{Ncl}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))} = 1_N$ which implies $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*})) = 1_N$. Since $\text{Nint} 1_N = 1_N$. Hence $\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}))$ Then $\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}$ is a N α OS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Since \check{f} is Npre- α -irresolute (N α -irresolute and N semi- α -irresolute, resp.), $\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*})$ is a NPOS (N α OS and NSOS, resp.) in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$ is a \mathcal{NPCS} (N α CS and NSCS, resp.) in \mathcal{X}_N .

Theorem 4.2 If a function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ is Npre- β -irresolute, then $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$ is \mathcal{NPCS} in \mathcal{X}_N for any Nnowheredense set \mathcal{E}_1^* of \mathcal{Y}_N .

Proof: Let \mathcal{E}_1^* be an Nnowhere dense set in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) = 0_N$. Now, $\overline{\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))} = 1_N \Rightarrow \overline{\text{Ncl}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))} = 1_N$ which implies $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*})) = 1_N$ Since $\text{Nint} 1_N = 1_N$ and $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*})) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}))$. Hence $\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*} \subseteq 1_N = \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*})) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}))$. Then $\overline{\mathcal{E}_1^*}$ is a $\mathcal{N}\beta$ OS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Since \check{f} is Npre- β -irresolute, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$ is a \mathcal{NPCS} in \mathcal{X}_N .

Theorem 4.3 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ from an NTS \mathcal{X}_N into an NTS \mathcal{Y}_N is Npre- α -irresolute if and only if for each NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N and N α OS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$, there exists an NPOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$.

Proof: Let \check{f} be any Npre- α -irresolute function. $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{E}_2^* be any N α OS in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Let $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Then \mathcal{E}_1^* is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N which containing NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Conversely, let \mathcal{E}_2^* be a N α OS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. According to an assumption, there exists an NPOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Hence $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Also $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Therefore, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ is NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus, \check{f} is a Npre- α -irresolute function.

Theorem 4.4 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ from an NTS \mathcal{X}_N into an NTS \mathcal{Y}_N is α -irresolute if and only if for each NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N and NaOS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$, there exists an NaOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$.

Proof: Let \check{f} be any α -irresolute function. $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{E}_2^* be any NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \text{Naint } \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Let $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \text{Naint } \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Then \mathcal{E}_1^* is a NaOS in \mathcal{X}_N which containing NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \check{f}(\text{Naint } \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) = f(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Conversely, let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. According to an assumption, there exists an NaOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Hence $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ and $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* = \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \text{Naint } \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Since $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an arbitrary NP and $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is union of all NPs containing in $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$, which gives that $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint } \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NaOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is a α -irresolute function.

Theorem 4.5 \mathcal{E}_1^* function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ from an NTS \mathcal{X}_N into an NTS \mathcal{Y}_N is N semi- α -irresolute if and only if for each NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N and NaOS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$, there exists an NSOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$.

Proof: Let \check{f} be any NS- α -irresolute function, $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{E}_2^* be any NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Let $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Then \mathcal{E}_1^* is a NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N which containing NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \check{f}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$

Conversely, let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$.

According to an assumption, there exists an NSOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N

such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Hence $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Also $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$

Therefore, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ is NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is a NS- α -irresolute function

Theorem 4.6 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ from an NTS \mathcal{X}_N into an NTS \mathcal{Y}_N is N pre- β -irresolute if and only if for each NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N and $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$, there exists an NPOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$.

Proof: Let \check{f} be any Npre- β -irresolute mapping. $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{E}_2^* be any $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Let $\mathcal{E}_1^* = \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Then \mathcal{E}_1^* is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N which containing NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) = \check{f}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$.

Conversely, let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N and $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$.

According to an assumption, there exists an NPOS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N such that $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^*$ and $\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Hence $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. Also $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$.

Therefore, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ is NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence \check{f} is a Npre- β -irresolute function.

Theorem 4.7 A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ from an NTS \mathcal{X}_N into an NTS \mathcal{Y}_N is N pre- α -irresolute if and only if for each NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N and NaOS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$, $\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NN of NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

Proof: Let \check{f} be any Npre- α -irresolute function. $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{E}_2^* be any NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is IFN of $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

Conversely, let \mathcal{E}_2^* be a NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N and $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$

According to an assumption, $\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is NN of NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N . So $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N .

Therefore \check{f} is a Npre- α -irresolute function.

Theorem 4.8:

A function $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ from an NTS \mathcal{X}_N into an NTS \mathcal{Y}_N is N pre- β -irresolute if and only if for each NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N and $\mathcal{N}\beta OS \mathcal{E}_2^*$ in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*, Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$, is a NN of NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

Proof: Let \check{f} be any Npre- β -irresolute function. $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N and \mathcal{E}_2^* be any $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$. Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$.

Hence $Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ is IFN of $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

Conversely, let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N and $p(\alpha, \beta)$ be an NP in \mathcal{X}_N such that $\check{f}(p(\alpha, \beta)) \in \mathcal{E}_2^*$.

Then $p(\alpha, \beta) \in \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ According to an assumption, $Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ is nN of NP $p(\alpha, \beta)$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

Thus $p(\alpha, \beta) \in Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$, so $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N .

Therefore \check{f} is a Npre- β -irresolute function.

Theorem 4.9

The following hold for functions $\check{f}: \mathcal{X}_N \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}_N$ and $\check{g}: \mathcal{Y}_N \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}_N$

- i) If \check{f} is Npre irresolute and g is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.), then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is N pre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.) function.
- ii) If \check{f} is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.), and g is $\mathcal{N}\beta$ - continuous, (resp.), then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is N pre continuous.
- iii) If \check{f} is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.) and g is $\mathcal{N}\beta$ - irresolute, (resp.), then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.).
- iv) If \check{f} is NS- α -irresolute ($\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute, resp.) and g is IF α -continuous, then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is N Semi continuous ($\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -continuous, resp.).
- v) If \check{f} is NS- α -irresolute ($\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute, resp.) and g is IF α -irresolute, then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is NS- α -irresolute ($\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute, resp.).
- vi) If \check{f} is Nirresolute and g is NS- α -irresolute, then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is NS- α -irresolute.
- vii) If \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute and g is Nstrongly α -continuous, then $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is Nstrongly α -continuous.

Proof:

(i) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ ($\mathcal{N}\beta OS$, resp.) in \mathcal{Z} . Since g is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.) $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now $(\check{g} \circ \check{f})^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Since \check{f} is Npre irresolute, $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.).

(ii) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NOS in \mathcal{Z} . Since g is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -continuous ($\mathcal{N}\beta$ -continuous, resp.), $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ ($\mathcal{N}\beta OS$, resp.) in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now $(\check{g} \circ \check{f})^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Since \check{f} is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.), $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is Npre continuous.

(iii) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ ($\mathcal{N}\beta OS$, resp.) in \mathcal{Z} . Since g is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute ($\mathcal{N}\beta$ -irresolute, resp.), $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ ($\mathcal{N}\beta OS$ resp.) in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now $(\check{g} \circ \check{f})^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Since \check{f} is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.), $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NPOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is Npre- α -irresolute (Npre- β -irresolute, resp.).

(iv) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NOS in \mathcal{Z} . Since g is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -continuous, $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is an $\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now $(\check{g} \circ \check{f})^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Since \check{f} is NS- α -irresolute ($\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute, resp.), $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NSOS ($\mathcal{N}\alpha OS$, resp.) in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is NSemi continuous ($\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -continuous, resp.).

(v) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NaOS in Z . Since g is Na-irresolute, $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is an NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now Since \check{f} is NS- α -irresolute (Na-irresolute, resp.), $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NSOS (NaOS, resp.) in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is NS- α -irresolute (Na-irresolute, resp.).

(vi) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NaOS in Z . Since g is NS- α -irresolute, $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NSOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now $(\check{g} \circ \check{f})^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Since \check{f} is Nirresolute, $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NSOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is NS- α -irresolute.

(vii) Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NSOS in Z . Since g is Nstrongly α -continuous $\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Now $(\check{g} \circ \check{f})^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Since \check{f} is Na-irresolute, $\check{f}^{-1}(\check{g}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ is a NaOS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{g} \circ \check{f}$ is Nstrongly α -continuous.

5. CHARACTERIZATIONS

In this section, several characterizations of Neutrosophic pre- α -irresolute functions, Neutrosophic α -irresolute functions, Neutrosophic semi- α -irresolute functions and Neutrosophic pre- β -irresolute functions are established

Theorem 5.1 If \check{f} is a function from an NTS $(\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N)$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$, then the following are equivalent.

- (a) \check{f} is a Npre- α -irresolute.
- (b) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{int}(cl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ for every NaOS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (c) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is NPCCS in \mathcal{X}_N for every NaCS \mathcal{E}_3^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (d) $Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$ for every NS \mathcal{E}_4^* of \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (e) $\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{E}_5^*))) \subseteq Naclf(\mathcal{E}_5^*)$ for every NS \mathcal{E}_5^* of \mathcal{X}_N .

Proof:

(a) \Rightarrow (b): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (a), $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is NPCCS in \mathcal{X}_N . $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence (a) \Rightarrow (b) is proved.

(b) \Rightarrow (c): Let \mathcal{E}_3^* be any NaCS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}$ is NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (b), $(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))$. But $\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)} \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = Nint(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))$. This implies $\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) \Rightarrow Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is NPCCS in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence (b) \Rightarrow (c) is proved.

(c) \Rightarrow (d): Let \mathcal{E}_4^* be an NS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $Nacl(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is Na-closed in \mathcal{Y}_N . $\Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$ is NPCCS in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_4^*)))) \subseteq (Nacl(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$ Hence (c) \Rightarrow (d) is proved.

(d) \Rightarrow (e): Let \mathcal{E}_5^* be an NS in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))) \subseteq Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq Nacl(\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))$.

Thus $\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{E}_5^*))) \subseteq Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*))$. Hence (d) \Rightarrow (e) is proved.

(e) \Rightarrow (a): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an NaOS in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} = Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ is a NS in \mathcal{X}_N . By (e),

$$\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq Nacl(\check{f}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq Nacl(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}) = \overline{Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} = \overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$$

Thus, $\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq Nacl(\check{f}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq \overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$. -----(1)

Consider

$$\overline{Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))} = \overline{Ncl(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))} = Ncl(Nint(\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)}) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))))))$$
-----(2)

By (1) and (2), $\overline{Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))} \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}\check{f}(Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}))) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is \mathcal{NPOS} in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \check{f} is $\mathcal{Npre-}\alpha$ -irresolute. Hence (e) \Rightarrow (a) is proved.

Theorem 5.2 If $\check{f}: (\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N) \rightarrow (\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$ be a mapping from NTS \mathcal{X}_N into NTS \mathcal{Y}_N .

Then the following are equivalent.

- (a) \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute.
- (b) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N for each $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (c) $\check{f}(NaclA) \subseteq Naclf(\mathcal{E}_1^*)$ for each NS \mathcal{E}_1^* in \mathcal{X}_N .
- (d) $Nacl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ for each NS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (e) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\alpha \text{ int } \mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\alpha \text{ int } \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ for each NS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .

Proof:

(a) \Rightarrow (b): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$ is $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Since \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute, $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)}$ is $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus (a) \Rightarrow (b) is proved.

(b) \Rightarrow (c): Let \mathcal{E}_1^* be NS in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $\mathcal{E}_1^* \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)))$. As $Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))$ is $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N , by (b), $\check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*)))$ is a $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . $Nacl(\mathcal{E}_1^*) \subseteq Nacl((Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))) = Nacl(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_1^*))$ Hence (b) \Rightarrow (c) is proved.

(c) \Rightarrow (d): For any NS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N , let $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \mathcal{E}_1^*$ By (c), $\check{f}(Nacl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq Nacl\check{f}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) \subseteq Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. and $acl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(Nacl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(Nacl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$

Thus $Nacl\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$ Hence (c) \Rightarrow (d) is proved.

(d) \Rightarrow (e): For any NS \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N , $Naint(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \overline{Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*)}$. Now $\check{f}^{-1}(Naint(\mathcal{E}_2^*)) = \check{f}^{-1}(\overline{Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*)}) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_2^*))} = \overline{Nacl\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} = \overline{Naint\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} \subseteq Naint\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$

(e) \Rightarrow (a): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\mathcal{E}_2^* = Naint(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ and $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Naint(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$. By definition $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \supseteq Naint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. So $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) = Naint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Thus $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is a $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N which implies \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -irresolute. Thus (e) \Rightarrow (a) is proved.

Theorem 5.3 If \check{f} is a function from an $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N)$ to another NTS $(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$, then the following are equivalent.

- (a) \check{f} is a $\mathcal{NS-}\alpha$ -irresolute.
- (b) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ for every $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ \mathcal{E}_2^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (c) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is $\mathcal{NSemiclosed}$ in \mathcal{X}_N for every $\mathcal{N}\alpha$ -closed set \mathcal{E}_3^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (d) $Nint(Ncl(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(Nacl(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$ for every NS \mathcal{E}_4^* of \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (e) $\check{f}(Nint(NclE)) \subseteq Naclf(\mathcal{E}_5^*)$ for every NS \mathcal{E}_5^* of \mathcal{X}_N .

Proof: (a) \Rightarrow (b):

Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (a), $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is \mathcal{NSOS} in \mathcal{X}_N . $\Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq Ncl(Nint \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))$. Hence (a) \Rightarrow (b) is proved.

(b)⇒(c): Let \mathcal{E}_3^* be any $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}$ is a $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (b), $\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}))$. But $\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)} \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)}) = \text{Ncl}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) = \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\text{Semiclosed}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Hence (b)⇒(c) is proved.

(c)⇒(d): Let \mathcal{E}_4^* be an $\mathcal{N}\text{S}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{-cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{-closed}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (c) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$ is $\mathcal{N}\text{Semiclosed}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$. Hence (c)⇒(d) is proved.

(d)⇒(e): Let \mathcal{E}_5^* be an $\mathcal{N}\text{S}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*))))$ Therefore $\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))$.

Consequently $\check{f}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*))$. Hence (d) ⇒(e) is proved.

(e)⇒(a): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)}$ is a $\mathcal{N}\text{S}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . By (e), $\check{f}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\check{f}(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\alpha\text{cl}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}) = \overline{\mathcal{N}\alpha\text{int}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} = \overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$ Thus, $\check{f}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}))) \subseteq \overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}$. -----(1)

$$\text{Consider } \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \text{Nint}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) = \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*})))$$

$$\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))) \text{-----(2)}$$

By (1) and (2),

$$\overline{\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))} \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(\text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))))$$

$$\subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)} \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*))) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \text{ is } \mathcal{N}\text{SOS} \text{ in } \mathcal{X}_N.$$

Thus \check{f} is $\mathcal{N}\text{S-}\alpha\text{-irresolute}$. Hence (e)⇒(a) is proved.

Theorem 5.4 If \check{f} is a function from an $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathcal{X}_N, \mathcal{T}_N)$ to another $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathcal{Y}_N, \mathcal{G}_N)$, then the following are equivalent.

- (a) \check{f} is a $\mathcal{N}\text{pre-}\beta\text{-irresolute}$.
- (b) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{int}(\text{cl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$ for every $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS } \mathcal{E}_2^*$ in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (c) $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\text{PCS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N for every $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -closed set \mathcal{E}_3^* in \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (d) $\text{cl}(\text{int}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{clD})$ for every $\mathcal{N}\text{S } \mathcal{E}_4^*$ of \mathcal{Y}_N .
- (e) $\check{f}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(\mathcal{E}_5^*))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)$ for every $\mathcal{N}\text{S } \mathcal{E}_5^*$ of \mathcal{X}_N .

Proof: (a)⇒(b): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (a), $\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\text{POS}$ in $\mathcal{X}_N \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)))$. Hence (a)⇒(b) is proved.

(b)⇒(c): Let \mathcal{E}_3^* be any $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{CS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}$ is $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (b), $\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*}) \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_3^*})))$. But $\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)} \subseteq \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)}) = \text{Nint}(\text{Ncl}(\text{int}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))) = \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)))$.

This implies $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*) \Rightarrow \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_3^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\text{PCS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

Hence (b) ⇒(c) is proved.

(c)⇒(d): Let \mathcal{E}_4^* be an $\mathcal{N}\text{S}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)$ is $\mathcal{N}\beta$ -closed in \mathcal{Y}_N . By (c), $\overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))}$ is $\mathcal{N}\text{PCS}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$

$$\text{Thus } \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*)))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\mathcal{E}_4^*))$$

Hence (c) ⇒(d) is proved.

(d)⇒(e):

Let \mathcal{E}_5^* be an $\mathcal{N}\text{S}$ in \mathcal{X}_N . Then $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))$ then $\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)) \subseteq \check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*)))$. This implies $\check{f}(\text{Ncl}(\text{Nint}(\mathcal{E}_5^*))) \subseteq \mathcal{N}\beta\text{cl}(\check{f}(\mathcal{E}_5^*))$. Hence (d)⇒(e) is proved.

(e)⇒(a): Let \mathcal{E}_2^* be an $\mathcal{N}\beta\text{OS}$ in \mathcal{Y}_N . Then $\check{f}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}_2^*}) = \overline{\check{f}^{-1}(\mathcal{E}_2^*)}$ is a $\mathcal{N}\text{S}$ in \mathcal{X}_N .

By (e), $\overline{\mathcal{N}cl(Nint(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*)))} \subseteq N\beta cl\overline{\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*)} \subseteq \overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^* \dots \dots (1)$ Consider $\overline{Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*))}$

$$= \overline{Ncl(Ncl(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*))} = Nint(\overline{Ncl(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*))} \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*))) \subseteq \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*)}) \dots \dots (2)$$

By (1) and (2), $\overline{Nint(Ncl(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*))} \subseteq \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*)}) \subseteq \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*) = \overline{\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*)}$ This implies $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*) \subseteq Nint(\overline{Ncl(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*))}$ which proves $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\overline{\mathcal{E}}_2^*)$ is *NPOS* in \mathcal{X}_N . Thus \mathcal{F} is pre- β -irresolute. Hence (e) \Rightarrow (a) is proved.

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Received: Sep 8, 2020. Accepted: Jan 7, 2021